

A Review on Rasamanjari: It's Contribution in Pharmaceutical Science

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is an ancient science. Rasashastra and bhaishajya kalpana is one of the important branch of Ayurveda. Rasamanjari is one of the compile text written by Acharya Shalinath. Hindi translation Siddhiprada written by Prof. Siddhi Nandan Mishra. Rasashastra is not included in Astang Ayurveda. Rasashastra deals with minerals and metals. Purification of mineral metals and their formulation are clearly described in Rasamanjari. The pharmaceutical contribution of Rasamanjari is very beneficial for modern era.

Keywords: Rasashastra, Rasamanjari, Minerals, Metals etc.

INTRODUCTION

In ancient Ayurveda, the emphasis has been over the herbs and their therapeutic usages. Later on the animal product, metals and minerals started to find favor of the Ayurvedic practitioners. The minerals and metals are very effective the potent for immunization, rejuvenation and elimination of disease. The study of Dehavada and the use of metals were successful and it was found that the Mercury was very effective when

compared to its other minerals and herbals counterparts. ⁽¹⁾Rasamanjari is one of the compiled text written by ShriShalinath son of ShriVaidyanath. Its time period is 15th century. Total 10 *adhyaya* are mentioned. Shri *shalinath's* time period his family and where the author belong these many questions are not answered yet. First published by Shri *KrushnaDas, ShriGangavishnu, ShriKrushanlal*. Hindi translation SIDDHIPRADA by Professor Siddhinandan Mishra. Rasamanjari is also mentioned in Rasendra-saar-sangrah. Rasamanjari starts with *Ganaptibandana* and *Saraswatibandana*.⁽²⁾

MATERIALS & METHODS

Rasamanjari has 10 chapters, starting from description of parada and its importance in Alchemy. Each chapter of the book has its own importance. Its 7th chapter also named as Rasayanadhikar and 10th chapter is named as Arishtavigyaan because it's explained regarding *Arista* as a prognostic symptom. It is not only a text of Alchemy but also used as a medical treatise. All the chapters of Rasamanjari explained below.

1st chapter

Total 37 *shlokas*. Description of *Parad*(Mercury), Importance of *Parad*, *GunaDoshaShodhan* of *Parad*. *Shuddha-AshuddhaParadlakshan*. *Guru* and *shishyalakshan*. *Taptakhalwa*. *Hingulothaparavidhi* and *guna*.⁽³⁾

2nd chapter

This chapter explains about *ParadMaran*, *Jaarna*, Gold *Jaarna*, *Murchhna*. Process of making of 8 types *Rasasindoor*. Three types of making of *Rasakarpoor*. Explains about *guna* and *lakshan* of *Murchhit* and *MaaritParad*. Characteristics of *BaddhaParad*. And *pathya-apathya* during *Paradsevenkaal*. *Rasakarpoor* is a *Kupipakwarasayan* but *ShriShalinath* clearly mentioned *DhamanYantra* for making of *Rasakarpoor*.⁽⁴⁾

3rd chapter

This chapter contains 102 *shlokas*. Explains about 20 *Uprasa*. *Samanyashodhan*, *maran* of *Uprasa*. Also explain *ssamanyashodhan* and *maran* of *Ratnas*.

Four types of *GandhakRakta*, *Peet*, *Shweta*, *Krishna*. *RaktaGandhak* is used for *Dhatuwaad*, *PeetGandhak* is used for *Rasayankarma*, *Shweta* is used for *vraandi*, *KrishnaGandhak* is rare and very useful. *Rasaraj* term used for *Gandhak*. *GandhakDruti* is also named as *Gandhaktaila*. Four types of *Heerak*. Eight types of *Vaikrant* according to *varna*. *Satwapatan* of *vaikrant* also explained. Four types of *Abhrak*. Explained about *Dhanyabhramak* making, *Abhrakdravan*. Explained *Bhoonagsatwapatan* and *Mudrikanirmaan*. Three types of *CovriesSardhnishka*, *nishka*, *paadonnishka*.⁽⁵⁾

4th chapter

In this chapter 18 type of *Kandavish*. *Lakshan*, *bheda*, *shodhan* of poison & antidote of *vish*. According to *varna* four type of *vishBrahmin*, *Kshatriya*, *Vaishya* and *Shudra*. *Vishsevan* according to *ritukaal* (If *shuddhavish* taken in *Sharad*, *Grishma*, *Basant* and *Varsharitu* then it destroy *kustha* and *lootavish* effect.). Also explain about *vishveganashaktanmantra*.⁽⁶⁾

5th chapter

In this chapter general and specific *shodhan* of *Dhatu*. *Maran* and *gunadharam* of *dhatu*. Explain about *suvarn*, *rajat*, *tamra*, *lauh*, *naag*, *vang*, *yashad*, *pittal*, *kansya* and *vart*. 8 doshas of copper. *Apathya*

during *lauhsevankaal* also explains *mandoor*. *Nirutthikaran* of *lauha* explained.⁽⁷⁾

6th chapter

This chapter contains 345 *shlokas*. Chapter starts with *Dhanvantarivandana*. Explains the importance of *rasavaidya*. In this chapter 81 *anubhoot* and *pramanityoga*. Importance of *mantra* for *Rasusadhi*.⁽⁸⁾

7th chapter

This chapter is also known as **Rasayanadhikaar**. Explains the process of *kshetrikaran*. Four *rasayan* yoga explains *Gandhamruta* *rasayan*, *Hemsunder* *rasayan*, *Mrutasanjivani* *Gutika*, *Viryarodhini* *Gutika*.⁽⁹⁾

8th chapter

This chapter contains 28 *shlokas*. Explains *yoga* for *netrarog*, Making process of *anjana*, *matra* and types. *Dantaadivarti* for *savranshukra* and *avranshukra*. Use of *anjana* after *doshpaak* mentioned. *Pratyanjana*, *Keshranjantaila* and *palitroganashakyoga* explained. *Anjanavartimatra* one *harenu* for *tikshna*, 1½ for *madhyamand* 2 *harenu* for *mriduanjana*.⁽¹⁰⁾

9th chapter

total *yoga* explained 9 *veeryasthambhanyoga*, *lingsthulikaranyoga*, *lingdhwastikaranyoga*, 3 *shandhatwakaranyoga*, *shandhatwanashanyoga*, *streedraavanyoga*, *strivashikaranyoga*, *vidweshikaran*, *lomshatan*, *lomapatanyoga*, *bandhyakaranyoga*, *garbhstrawkaryoga*, *garbhpradayoga*, *sukhprasavayoga*. Also explained about *Baaltantra*, 16 *yoginis*. And *bali*, *mantra*, *dishapuja* for *yoginishanti*.⁽¹¹⁾

10th chapter

This is last chapter of *Rasamanjari*. Also named **Aristavigyaan**. This chapter is about *aristakaal*. *Aristalakshan* of day, month, year. Symptoms of *chhayapurush*. This is only *rasa* text which explained regarding *Arista* as a prognostic symptom.⁽¹²⁾

UNIQUE CONTRIBUTION

- *Rasamanjari* has mentioned *DhamanYantra* for making *Rasakarpoor*.
- *Rasaraj* term used for *Gandhak*.

- Explanation of *Baltantra* and 16 *yoginis* in 9th chapter.
- This is only rasa text which explained about *Arista* as a prognostic system.

DISCUSSION

Overall Rasamanjari is a compile text which is very useful as a reference. In this book complete description of Parad (Mercury) and its purification and formulations. *Shodhan, Maran of Uprasa, Vish and Dhatus*. Also explains *Rasayanyoga, Arista* as a prognostic system, *Baltantra and yoginis*. In 1st chapter it's mainly described parad shodhan and guru shishya lakshan. Marana, jarana, murchhana, 8 types of rasasindoor, and 3 types of Rasakarpoor is described in 2nd chapter. In 3rd chapter classification of rasa dravyas and in 4th chapter it explained vish classification. In 5th chapter Dhatu shodhan (purification of metals) and in 6th chapter Dhanwantari vandana and 81 anubhoot and pramanit yoga is described. Kshetrikaran explained in 7th chapter and different type of anjana and medicine for netra roga are described in 8th chapter. In 9th chapter different types of yoga, 16 yoginis and Baaltantra is mentioned and in last chapter of Rasamanjari Arista lakshan is explained. In Rasamanjari wide range of rasa medicine preparation is explained. Its 7th chapter also named as Rasayanadhikar and 10th chapter is named as Arishtavigyaan because it's explained regarding *Arista* as a prognostic symptom.

CONCLUSION

This book is practically very useful. It is a compilation Alchemy along with many important creations and modifications of its own. This book can be taken as by the virtue of it's practical usefulness. The subject matter of the Rasamanjari of focused on performance and alternative methods of experimentation and medicine preparations. It has given unique contribution in its own experience. Rasamanjari is one of the finest text of its contemporary era.

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